

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners' Network

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1. Summary

This deliverable considers the practitioners' gaps and needs as identified thus far through the CYCLOPES project and views them through a policy lens. Firstly, we discuss commonalities between the EU policy environment and the topics explored through the CYCLOPES workshops, identifying synergies and complementarities. Secondly, we take the publicly available gaps and needs identified across the five pillars of technology, process, people, organization and legal and highlight where these align with forthcoming and proposed policy actions and where further investment may be required to better support practitioners. Finally, we look to the future at emerging topics from the policy environment, CYCLOPES and upcoming research topics to guide potential uptake of the outcomes of CYCLOPES as well as potential new areas for the project to consider.

2. Overview of Cyclopes

The HORIZON 2020 project CYCLOPES (Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners Network) aims to build a stable European network of law enforcement agencies to effectively combat cybercrime. It is a five-year network project with 21 partners from 14 different EU countries. The partners come from EU law enforcement agencies, research institutes, universities and companies. The lead lies with the Polish Platform for Homeland Security (PPHS). The project started in May 2021.

In addition to setting up the network, the core of the project is the joint transfer of knowledge to security authorities and participation in standardization recommendations. In thematically predefined user workshops, gaps and requirements, but also the current status of the authorities for combating cybercrime, are determined. A list of priorities with an increased need for standardization is also created. The workshops are held three times a year on the overarching subject areas:

- Cybercrime – Affecting People Directly
- Cybercrime – Affecting Systems
- Digital Forensics

The outcomes of the workshops lead to a list of available tools, software and research opportunities that may help address some of the gaps, needs and challenges identified for each thematic area. Each year, one workshop provides the inspiration for a Joint Live Exercise – an opportunity for solution providers and practitioners to come together to trial available solutions linked to the gaps and challenges identified.

The purpose of this deliverable is to produce a policy paper on practitioners needs and requirements. Our approach considers the EU policy environment in relation to the area of cybercrime correlated with the publicly available information on practitioners needs and requirements emerging from the research in CYCLOPES.

3. EU Policy Environment for Security and Cybercrime

Within the EU policy environment, cybercrime is both a topic in and of itself and an important factor in several crime types that are strategically important for the EU. Furthermore, CYCLOPES' focus across the three strands, digital forensics, cybercrime affecting systems and cybercrime affecting people, highlights the number of crime areas that cybercrime now covers. This section will highlight the main themes within the current policy environment that overlap with CYCLOPES' identified practitioner needs and requirements emerging from the project's first three years.

Neatly aligning with the delivery cycle for CYCLOPES, the **EU Security Union Strategy 2020 – 2025**¹ provides the foundation for the current policy cycle within the security context. Emerging from the first months of the COVID-19 pandemic into a rapidly changing threat landscape, the strategy emphasized the shift towards cyber-related crime due to the growth in the use of technologies. In the first incarnation of the strategy, four of the critical actions related to the need to tackle evolving threats are closely linked to CYCLOPES and the needs of practitioners; these are [...] *cybercrime legislation is implemented and fit for purpose*; [...] *a more effective fight against child sexual abuse*; [...] *detection and removal of child sexual abuse material*; and [...] *enhance law enforcement capacity in digital investigations*. Furthermore, the strategy also highlighted the need to consider the impact of the growing use of cryptocurrencies, mechanisms for cooperation and information exchange (both in terms of process and technology) and the need to improve skills and raise awareness, especially in cybercrime, for law enforcement. These themes have all been reflected in CYCLOPES activities to date.

As the security landscape has evolved in the last four years, the European Commission has regularly assessed progress and updated the strategy to reflect such an ever-changing environment. The first update² highlighted continuing growth in malware and ransomware threats, concerns about the increase of child sexual abuse material (CSAM) and how this links to the proposal for a new strategy from the EU in the more effective fight against CSA³ and the publication of the SIRIUS EU Digital Evidence Situation Report.⁴ As discussed in the outputs from WP7, which focused on legal, ethical and societal aspects, of CYCLOPES, the E-Evidence package⁵ also progressed during this period, helping to map out a future for better cross-border access to electronic evidence.

In the second progress update⁶, efforts to continue to step up the fight against ransomware were prioritized, while also recognizing the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for crime and law enforcement agencies (LEAs). Specific considerations relating to online investigations and electronic data, including the ability to access and retain such data, were also brought forward

¹ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on the EU Security Union Strategy (COM/2020/605 final) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0605>

² First Progress Report and Annexes on the EU Security Union Strategy (December 2021) https://commission.europa.eu/publications/first-progress-report-and-annexes-eu-security-union-strategy_en

³ European Commission (2024) Child sexual abuse. https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/internal-security/child-sexual-abuse_en

⁴ Europol (2024) SIRIUS EU Electronic Evidence Situation Report 2023 <https://www.europol.europa.eu/publications-events/publications/sirius-eu-electronic-evidence-situation-report-2023>

⁵ European Commission (2023) E-evidence - cross-border access to electronic evidence https://commission.europa.eu/law/cross-border-cases/judicial-cooperation/types-judicial-cooperation/e-evidence-cross-border-access-electronic-evidence_en

⁶ European Commission (2021) Second Progress Report and Annexes on the EU Security Union Strategy https://commission.europa.eu/publications/second-progress-report-and-annexes-eu-security-union-strategy_en

to provide better ongoing support to investigators in the future – this has also been a recurring theme within CYCLOPES. A significant emerging topic in this period also centred around encryption, with the progress update specifically highlighting how to increase capacity and capabilities to deal with encrypted information, in some parts addressed by the launch of Europol's decryption facility.⁷ Recognizing improved judicial cooperation as a necessity was also highlighted at this stage, while the greater role of the online element in organized crime was also highlighted as becoming an increasingly important factor.

The third update considers the period up to December 2021,⁸ with the Second Additional Protocol of the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime⁹ formally concluding, which provides better support for international cooperation on cybercrime and digital evidence, complementing the E-Evidence package. This also coincided with the preparation of a new UN Cybercrime Convention. An important output during this period for CYCLOPES was the Eurojust-Europol EU Digital Evidence Situation Report¹⁰, which considered the interaction between judicial, law enforcement, and online service providers in the use of electronic evidence while encryption was again highlighted as an area of concern via Europol observatory function¹¹ with a fourth update expected soon. Meanwhile, the fourth update¹² was dominated by the emergence of Russia's war against Ukraine, particularly in light of a rise in cyberattacks, with an acknowledgement that cybercriminals were looking to exploit the war to their advantage through various forms of organized crime activity.

The fifth update¹³, delivered in December 2022, served as a mid-term overview and update of the strategy, providing timely reminders on the continuing threat from ransomware, the launch of the Europol decryption platform, and the increasing scale of CSA and CSAM online – again all highly relevant to CYCLOPES' activities. However, a new and emerging threat highlighted was the growth in 'gender-based cyber violence' mainly targeted against women and girls, a topic not considered by the project to date. Finally, the most recent report¹⁴ began to place a greater emphasis on building links between cyber and physical threats, with the report itself highly focused on legislative progress, especially that related to the fight against child sexual exploitation, including the proposal of a new EU Centre to support online platforms. Building on the previous update, the Commission also formally brought forward a directive on Combatting Violence against Women, with a specific consideration for cyber violence.¹⁵ A high-

⁷ Europol (2020) Europol and the European Commission inaugurate new decryption platform to tackle the challenge of encrypted material for law enforcement investigations. <https://www.europol.europa.eu/media-press/newsroom/news/europol-and-european-commission-inaugurate-new-decryption-platform-to-tackle-challenge-of-encrypted-material-for-law-enforcement>

⁸ European Commission (2021) Third Progress Report and Annexes on the EU Security Union Strategy https://commission.europa.eu/publications/third-progress-report-and-annexes-eu-security-union-strategy_en

⁹ Eurojust (2022) Second Additional Protocol to the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime and Cross-Border Access to Electronic Evidence <https://www.eurojust.europa.eu/publication/second-additional-protocol-budapest-convention-cybercrime-and-cross-border-access>

¹⁰ Europol-Eurojust (2021) SIRIUS EU Digital Evidence Situation Report 3rd Annual Report 2021. <https://www.europol.europa.eu/publications-events/publications/sirius-eu-digital-evidence-situation-report-3rd-annual-report-2021>

¹¹ Europol (2021) Third report of the observatory function on encryption <https://www.europol.europa.eu/publications-events/publications/third-report-of-observatory-function-encryption>

¹² European Commission (2022) Fourth Progress Report and Annexes on the EU Security Union Strategy https://commission.europa.eu/publications/fourth-progress-report-and-annexes-eu-security-union-strategy_en

¹³ European Commission (2022) Fifth Progress Report on the EU Security Union Strategy https://commission.europa.eu/publications/fifth-progress-report-eu-security-union-strategy_en

¹⁴ European Commission (2023) Sixth Progress Report on the EU Security Union Strategy https://commission.europa.eu/publications/sixth-progress-report-eu-security-union-strategy_en

¹⁵ European Parliament (2024) Parliament approves first ever EU rules on combating violence against women <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20240419IPR20588/parliament-approves-first-ever-eu-rules-on-combating-violence-against-women>

level group has now also been formed to tackle the several emerging aspects related to access to data, including encryption and data retention, with recommendations expected mid-2024.¹⁶

Beyond the SUS, DG Home also collates important developments in the area of cybercrime.¹⁷ This is classified into three main categories: (1) crimes specific to the internet; (2) online fraud and forgery; and (3) illegal content online. In particular, they recognize that many types of crime now have a digital component that crosses over into the cybercrime area. The priorities for the EU are to improve the prevention, investigation and prosecution of cybercrime and child sexual exploitation; build capacity in law enforcement and the judiciary; and work with industry to empower and protect citizens, all highly correlated with CYCLOPES's objectives.

Key horizontal issues in this area reflect those mentioned in the SUS, including both E-evidence and Encryption, as well as data retention concerning digital investigations. The Commission also highlights the critical role for Europol and EC3 in coordinating the fight against cybercrime in the Member States and with the judiciary.

As a practitioner network, CYCLOPES focuses on enhancing police and law enforcement cooperation and collaboration within the cybercrime area. Europe-wide Europol, of course, is mandated to facilitate law enforcement cooperation across all crime areas. This role also extends to support cooperation with private parties such as key industry players, including software providers, online service providers (OSPs), financial institutions, and others.¹⁸ Within Europol, the European Cybercrime Centre (EC3)¹⁹ has the mandate for the cybercrime area with the annual Internet Organized Crime Threat Assessment (IOCTA) as a key strategic output. The previous two IOCTA reports were published in 2021²⁰ and 2023²¹. In 2021, the report highlighted growing concerns around cybercrime-as-a-service, ransomware, mobile malware and DDOS attacks; numerous areas related to CSAM, online fraud and the impact of the dark web. In 2023, further reports highlighted the use of VPNs by cybercriminals, social engineering and remote desktop protocols and the emergence of an economy around stolen data.

The EU also has individual strategies for various crime areas that overlap with CYCLOPES elements. For example, the EU Strategy to tackle Organized Crime 2021 – 2025^{22,23} highlighted the need for a tailor-made response to specific types of crime, including cybercrime. Due focus was given to cyber-dependent crime in the wake of the pandemic, alongside CSE and the growth in the use of cryptocurrencies. Furthermore, the need for improvements in mechanisms and tools that support digital investigations and digital evidence capture and exchange were emphasized as being a key priority alongside solutions that address the

¹⁶ European Commission (2024) High-Level Group (HLG) on access to data for effective law enforcement https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/high-level-group-hlg-access-data-effective-law-enforcement_en

¹⁷ European Commission (n.d.) Cybercrime. https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/internal-security/cybercrime_en

¹⁸ European Commission (2022) Police cooperation – stronger mandate for Europol. https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/whats-new/police-cooperation-stronger-mandate-europol_en

¹⁹ Europol (n.d.) European Cybercrime Centre - EC3. <https://www.europol.europa.eu/about-europol/european-cybercrime-centre-ec3>

²⁰ Europol (2023) Internet Organised Crime Threat Assessment (IOCTA) 2021. <https://www.europol.europa.eu/publications-events/main-reports/internet-organised-crime-threat-assessment-iocta-2021>

²¹ Europol (2023) Internet Organised Crime Assessment (IOCTA) 2023. <https://www.europol.europa.eu/publication-events/main-reports/internet-organised-crime-assessment-iocta-2023>

²² European Commission (n.d.) Organised crime and human trafficking. https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/internal-security/organised-crime-and-human-trafficking_en

²³ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on the EU Strategy to tackle Organised Crime 2021-2025 (COM/2021/170 final) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0170>

challenges brought by encryption. Specifically, tools that support the gathering of open-source intelligence, cryptocurrency investigation and the dark web were given particular focus alongside highlighting some of the issues LEAs face around the use and awareness of open-source solutions, which should ultimately result in an analysis of the technological gaps and needs in the domain of digital investigation. This provides a specific opportunity for CYCLOPES to feed in its findings into this effort.

Concerning specific crime policies, whilst not directly aligned with cybercrime, the EU Drugs Strategy 2021-2025²⁴ and Agenda and Action Plan²⁵ all bring to the fore the need for better monitoring of online sources, including social media, apps and dark markets, which all cross-over into the challenges addressed by CYCLOPES. Similar priorities for internet monitoring are also discussed in the EU Strategy on Combatting Trafficking in Human Beings 2021-2025²⁶

Meanwhile, during recent years, the EU has invested significantly in policy surrounding CSE through the EU strategy for a more effective fight against child sexual abuse.²⁷ This strategy, which was launched in July 2020, culminated in the Proposal for a Regulation on preventing and combatting the sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children.²⁸ Regarding practitioners gaps and needs, the strategy outlined the need for better information sharing across Member States in relation to CSE and access to 'cutting edge technical capabilities'.

Finally, although counter-terrorism is somewhat separate from cybercrime, the Counter Terrorism Agenda,²⁹ and particularly the policies surrounding terrorist content online (TCO) and hate speech, share many similarities with those experienced with CYCLOPES. This is mainly seen in the areas that address the sharing of e-evidence and general information sharing across Member States as well as accessing information from online service providers.

Finally, another key facet of EU policy is the priorities set within the EMPACT Policy Cycle.³⁰ The current priorities of EMPACT, the European Multidisciplinary Platform Against Criminal Threats, were set for 2022 onwards and thus are well aligned with the implementation timeline of CYCLOPES. While EMPACT has several priority areas, for CYCLOPES, the specific priorities of cyber-attacks and CSE are of particular interest.

4. Embedding practitioners' needs within the EU policy environment

CYCLOPES has just reached the end of the third cycle of the project. Each year, the project has run three workshops addressing one of the three pillars of the project – digital forensics, cybercrime affecting systems, and cybercrime affecting people directly. These workshops

²⁴ Council of the European Union (2020) EU Drugs Strategy 2021-2025

<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-14178-2020-INIT/en/pdf>

²⁵ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions EU Agenda and Action Plan on Drugs 2021-2025

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0606>

²⁶ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on the EU Strategy on Combatting Trafficking in Human Beings 2021- 2025 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0171>

²⁷ European Commission (2024) Child sexual abuse. https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/internal-security/child-sexual-abuse_en

²⁸ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down rules to prevent and combat child sexual abuse (COM/2022/209 final) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2022%3A209%3AFIN>

²⁹ European Commission (n.d.) Counter terrorism and radicalisation. https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/internal-security/counter-terrorism-and-radicalisation_en

³⁰ Europol (2022) EU Policy Cycle – EMPACT. <https://www.europol.europa.eu/crime-areas-and-statistics/empact>

identify practitioners' challenges, gaps and needs across five key areas: technical, people, organizational, legal and process. An annual report on practitioners also complements these workshops needs relating to the dark web and quantum computing.

Table 1: CYCLOPES workshops in the first three years

	Digital Forensics	Cybercrime affecting People	Cybercrime affecting Systems
Year One	Mobile Devices and Wearables	Social Engineering	RDP Protocols
Year Two	Automotive Digital Forensics	Investigations involving Cloud Services	Cryptocurrency Investigations
Year Three	Internet of Things	Child Sexual Exploitation (CSE)	Cybercrime related Services

Firstly, CYCLOPES has made a significant effort to focus on identifying gaps, needs, challenges and priorities for cybercrime investigators in areas that align with the priorities of the EU. The efforts of CYCLOPES directly contribute to the stated aim of the SUS, which is to enhance law enforcement capacity in digital investigations. This occurs by CYCLOPES bringing practitioners together to share knowledge, identifying common challenges, available tools, and providing a mechanism to test out some of those tools. Furthermore, the more specific workshops on social engineering, RDP and cybercrime-related services are well aligned with the priorities identified as important topics in the IOCTA reports, mentioned above. This ensures CYCLOPES is addressing strategically important topics and those that require operational attention.

Furthermore, regarding the SUS, the workshops focused on cryptocurrency, CSE, and the separate focus on the dark web, which are, as highlighted in the previous section, also areas that have been specifically recognized as strategically important for the EU. For some workshops the priority needs identified are particular to the domain area (e.g., cryptocurrency, automotive forensics, RDP), while others are generalizable across cybercrime and digital investigations. Firstly, we'll describe the needs and priorities applicable across multiple areas, and later in the section, we will discuss some of the specific emerging requirements for individual topic areas.

In order to prepare this policy paper, we catalogued the main themes emerging from these workshops and then map them into those that are addressed within the existing policy environment and those that are still to be addressed. As only some of the deliverables this analysis is based on are public, the practitioners' needs are generalized where necessary.

Due to the nature of CYCLOPES' focus on cybercrime, a significant proportion of the needs and priorities identified fall under the remit of **technology or technical needs**. Access to software, hardware or support for technological processes are imperative for cybercrime practitioners and investigators. The need for better extraction, analysis, visualization, and reporting tools was flagged most highly by practitioners across all areas. In some ways, this is perhaps surprising because many tools on the market purport to address (automated) analysis and visualization in some form; however, this indicates that there is still a need for investment in tools that are specific to cybercrime investigation, improved access to state-of-the-art tools, and to ensure that the tools available keep pace with the needs of investigators. This is relevant as lack of access to capable tools for practitioners may mean they are consuming higher resources to complete the necessary analysis and/or cannot extract as much intelligence or

evidential value from the data as possible. Ultimately, in policy terms, this may also link to organizational issues highlighting the lack of access to tools, especially due to cost.

Another key need for practitioners already recognized in the policy environment is the challenges posed by various forms of **encryption** that either prevent or make access to data significantly more difficult. Particularly from mobile devices and data stored on cloud services, the increasing amount of data that is only accessible in encrypted format is posing a particular hurdle for investigators. This is also complementary to their need for support in **password bypassing**. Policy in this area, as referenced in the previous section, already recognizes that developments in encryption are already a major issue, not only for investigators but also for the detection of illegal content in other areas such as the distribution of CSAM and terrorist content online. While efforts have been initiated, such as through Europol's decryption facility, it is clear that this is likely to remain a priority need for some time.

While also mentioned in other categories, another important need highlighted by practitioners is the need for cross-border and cross-European collaboration, including specific **platforms and services that allow for information sharing**. This was mentioned directly for vehicle databases, CSEA material (especially that linked to Generative AI), and general intelligence sharing.

Access to technology and tools is also highlighted as a need not only for practitioners but also for first responders and is linked into the **people category** where **awareness raising, knowledge sharing and training** for all actors in the judicial process (first responders, investigators, digital forensics practitioners, and the judiciary) both in terms of increasing their overall knowledge but also to support the better use of the tools they have access to and to continue upskilling their knowledge as threats evolve and become more sophisticated. Such a requirement was brought up across numerous workshops and for all three themes, demonstrating that it is a cross-cutting need across the sector. Furthermore, practitioners highlighted a need for better education and awareness and citizens to ensure crucial intelligence and information are not deleted or reported.

While fewer needs have been mentioned under the **process theme**, this is largely due to its overlap with other categories. However, two relevant considerations highlighted were the need for better processes around the reporting, documentation, and information of similar and smaller cybercrimes that would allow for better **linking** between the modus operandi of these crimes. While improvements in **standardization** were also a recommendation that could be addressed at EU level, it is also being considered under WP4 in CYCLOPES.

Organizationally, the primary emerging theme was building relationships and improving access from law enforcement to third parties connected to the cybercrime ecosystem. This includes internet service providers (ISPs), industry and the private sector, tool providers, cloud service providers, and other law enforcement agencies both within and external to the EU. Furthermore, better **access to domain experts** and specialized teams for specific crimes was also highlighted, and building connections to academia was also mentioned. Other relevant organizational-related needs for practitioners also included improving overall **organizational knowledge** surrounding specific cybercrimes and the development of more **common dictionaries** and lexicons to support consistency in terminology. Finally, echoing the needs from the technology category, better support from LEAs as organizations to allow practitioners to get access to the tools they need to carry out their role effectively.

Finally, practitioners highlighted a lot of uncertainty around the legal spectre, including the **applicability of legislation such as GDPR** and differences between countries in the length

of time for data retention. A recurring theme surrounded support for **collaboration with other countries**, which included cross-border investigations and better provision of single points of contact for non-EU countries, especially for requests involving MLATs. The need for enabling LEAs to feed into legislative updates was also highlighted, while areas that LEAs feel are not currently well addressed by the legislation include support for takedowns and any legislation concerning the relationships to ISPs and VPNs and how they operate. Considering the e-evidence package, now that the legislation is in place, it is also important that its implementation is effectively supported and that practitioners can make full use of the opportunities it provides.

Referencing specific workshops, for **Cryptocurrency Investigation**³¹, the publicly identified priorities included the need for an end-to-end legal framework for crypto asset management (echoing other calls for updates to legislative frameworks, the need for an EU-level joint procurement group (again to support tool access), tools to support the growth in the use of privacy coins, tools specifically for tracing trace complex cryptocurrency transactions as well as their analysis and reporting. Uniquely, practitioners also noted the difficulty in attracting and retaining talent in this area and the need for better training across the whole sector, including the judiciary. Similarly, in the highly specific area of **automotive forensics**, needs such as access to live data and standardization of data access from the vehicle in general, better cooperation with manufacturers and support for EU vehicles were highlighted.

Another specific requirement that may align with some aspects of the new Europol Mandate as well as the Europol Tool Repository was the requirement from the cloud services workshop. In this workshop, practitioners expressed the need for access to test environments, sandboxes and standardized datasets that would allow them to validate tools and software consistently. Finally, considering recent developments in the area of combatting CSE initial needs emerging from the workshop, not previously addressed, included the need for more victim-centric approaches and numerous issues concerning the legislative environment, such as those relating to undercover investigations and, when in the case of emerging technologies such as VR and Generative AI, the lack of harmonization in legislation across different EU countries.

Separate to the workshops, CYCLOPES also produces each year a foresight report on the future needs of cybercrime investigators related to the dark web and quantum computing. While the specific outputs of the report are confidential, it is clear that the dark web continues to be a significant vector for the distribution of illegal material and the sale of illicit substances. Practitioners needs in this area were highly correlated with other priorities such as access to better tools, training and knowledge, legislative support for shutdowns and typical activities associated with open-source intelligence operations. For quantum computing the time horizon is further into the future and the potential impact is still somewhat speculative. Nonetheless, the findings from CYCLOPES in the year two report largely mirrored those identified by the most recent Europol Observatory Report.³²

CYCLOPES is still preparing the next round of workshop topics for the year four cycle, but it is clear that these should remain closely aligned with the current policy environment where possible. The next section wraps up the brief by presenting some future considerations.

³¹ <https://www.cyclopes-project.eu/news/gaps-needs-of-leas-in-the-area-of-cybercrime-as-a-facilitator-for-cybercrime>

³² Europol (2023) Exploring the second quantum revolution: new report. <https://www.europol.europa.eu/media-press/newsroom/news/exploring-second-quantum-revolution-new-report>

5. Impact on CYCLOPES and the future policy environment

The developments within CYCLOPES and within the EU policy environment highlight that there are still numerous areas within the cybercrime environment where existing tools, processes, policies and legislation are not fully meeting practitioners' needs for efficient investigation.

Meanwhile, there are also **topics emerging** within the policy environment that are yet to be considered within CYCLOPES. For example, except briefly in the case of CSE, the impact of developments in artificial intelligence as a threat vector or amplifier as well as the potential for cybercriminals to disrupt AI models through adversarial approaches are perhaps still a relatively niche area within cybercrime investigation. Separately, the new rules on combating violence against women particularly highlight the crimes of cyberstalking, cyber harassment, cyber flashing and cyber incitement. The extent to which LEAs and digital investigators are equipped to effectively investigate and prosecute these crimes are perhaps still underexplored in the cybercrime domain. Furthermore, this area is also linked to artificial intelligence through areas such as deep fakes and other forms of digital image manipulation. While the Directive³³ places responsibility on LEAs to investigate such offences, it is also necessary to consider if LEAs feel they are currently equipped, both through tools and knowledge, to effectively comply with the Directive and effectively investigate the crime or whether this represents a future gap or need.

There are existing R&I projects that are already addressing some of the proposed gaps and challenges identified by practitioners. As seen in recent report by the ENACT project³⁴ many projects have addressed topics such as the investigation of the dark web and dark markets. It is important to ensure these tools are able to ultimately filter through to practitioners. Similarly, the POLIICE project³⁵ considers how Quantum Computing may affect investigations in future, while STARLIGHT³⁶ addresses the use of AI including for cybercrime and adversarial uses. Previous projects have also developed solutions that support cryptocurrency investigations, including Titanium³⁷, TRACE³⁸, Anti-FinTer³⁹, and Cut-the-Cord⁴⁰. Other initiatives such as the Cyberspace project,⁴¹ efforts from EACTDA⁴² to support the continued development of tools and solutions in the cybercrime area can also provide significant benefits to practitioners.

CYCLOPES' results and outcomes to date also have the opportunity to directly inform and contribute to the **Horizon Europe** work programme. The calls for 2024 have significant alignment with the work already conducted by CYCLOPES. Specifically, we have mentioned the recognition from the CSE workshop that the legislative and organizational environment surrounding undercover investigations in this area needs improvement and this is already a facet of the HORIZON-CL3-2024-FCT-01-03 call on Lawful evidence collection in online child

³³ Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on combating violence against women and domestic violence (COM/2022/105 final) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022PC0105>

³⁴ <https://enact-eu.net/enact-publishes-first-analytical-report/>

³⁵ <https://poliice-project.eu/>

³⁶ <https://www.starlight-h2020.eu/>

³⁷ <https://www.titanium-project.eu/>

³⁸ <https://trace-illicit-money-flows.eu/>

³⁹ <https://anti-finter.eu/>

⁴⁰ <https://ctc-project.eu/>

⁴¹ <https://cyberspaceproject.eu/about/>

⁴² <https://www.eactda.eu/>

sexual abuse investigations, including undercover. Meanwhile, the HORIZON-CL3-2024-FCT-01-02 Open Topic provides a route to address many of the practitioners' needs related to (digital) forensics, including evidence collection and cross-border collaboration, as also recognized through CYCLOPES. Furthermore, there are also specific topics focused on the Internet of Things (HORIZON-CL3-2024-FCT-01-01) and Cryptocurrency Investigations (HORIZON-CL3-2024-FCT-01-08). Therefore, it is also important for CYCLOPES going forward that cybercrime practitioners' identified gaps and needs can feed into future research and innovation developments. This will help close the loop between the network of practitioners and other R&I activities while future identified gaps and needs could inform the work programme for 2025 and beyond.

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